

Impact of Board Diversity on the Financial Performance of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of board diversity on the financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Guided by the problem statement, objectives, and research questions, a literature review and secondary-data analysis were conducted using information drawn from the sampled firms' published financial statements, focusing on age diversity, gender diversity, educational diversity, nationality diversity, and financial performance over the ten-year period from 2013 to 2022. The Hausman test was used to choose between fixed-effects and random-effects estimation, and the fixed-effects model was adopted. The findings revealed a significant relationship between age, gender, national, and educational diversity and the financial performance of firms, with all four independent variables positively influencing the return on total assets of the sampled quoted manufacturing companies. The results confirm that board diversity enhances corporate governance and performance, while offering practical insights for organisations seeking to optimise financial outcomes through strategic diversity management. It is recommended that corporations develop and enforce policies that foster gender equality on their boards, including targeted recruitment, mentorship initiatives, and career-advancement programmes aimed at increasing the representation of women, younger members, and highly educated individuals in leadership roles, thereby harnessing their distinct perspectives and leadership approaches to promote equity and fairness within the board.

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Introduction

The necessity to strengthen corporate board performance over the last ten years has become more apparent, with high profile scandals and company failures such as Enron, Lehman Brothers and Volkswagen. These events forced regulatory agencies in both the U.S. and several developing nations to deal with corporate governance shortcomings. The financial sector has also seen corporate failures, particularly All States Trust Bank, Century Merchant Bank, African Express Bank, which failed due to bad corporate-governance practices and serious mismanagement (Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, 2022). The concept of diversity has been increasingly used in the literature on corporate-governance (Díaz-Fernández et al., 2020) and it has been subject of public debate (Naciti, 2019). This makes it even more important for companies to increase diversity among their board members.

As a result of successive corporate failures, Sarbanes–Oxley Act, UK Corporate Governance Code, professional pronouncements, the Nigerian SEC codes, Cadbury (1992) Report, Greenbury (1995) Report, Hampel (1998) Report and various codes of best practice on corporate governance have been amended to enhance corporate requirements, expectations, registration, reporting and stewardship guidelines. These changes speak to issues of board roles and responsibilities, the rights of shareholders, and the work of audit committees, enhancing the work of boards of directors and those entrusted with corporate governance, and protecting shareholders' financial interests.

Diversification means ensuring that people with different socio-economic characteristics and backgrounds are included to ensure that a board reflects the customers and stakeholders that it serves. The right board composition is essential for good corporate governance, as board composition influence board effectiveness, the board's performance of its duties and, ultimately, the firm's financial performance (Gordini & Rancati, 2017). The role of the board of directors is vital and irreplaceable as Soliman and Abd Elsalam (2012) believe it is at the heart of the corporate governance process due to its monitoring of senior management and to its assurance of the correctness of financial statements.

It is suggested that the more diverse a board is, the more interaction and exchange of ideas that will occur among the board members, which will have a positive effect on how well they understand the firm's environment (Nielsen & Huse, 2010). The quality of the board's decision-making, which can be improved by the skills and experience of the members and the outside resources the members add to the firm, can boost the firm's performance (Hsu et al., 2019). Diversity can help to improve teamwork and collaboration among board members as people with different genders, skills, backgrounds, cultures, ethnicities, educational backgrounds and viewpoints can work together to solve a range of important organisational issues (Society for Corporate Governance Nigeria, 2014).

There are two main types of board diversity identified by Kagzi and Guha (2018): structural diversity and demographic diversity. Structural diversity includes factors like board size, CEO duality and board independence, while demographic diversity includes factors like gender, ethnicity, education, age differences among board members etc. A diverse board is an indicator of an organization's willingness to hire a diverse workforce. Many different definitions of board diversity have been offered in literature. Board diversity can be defined as the composition of a board and its committees as described by Bjorklund (2010), or as the diversity in competencies, managerial experiences, personalities, learning styles, education, education, age, and values of board members as described by Mohammad et al. (2019).

There are several factors that can affect board diversity, such as age, gender, nationality, education and professional qualifications, life experiences, perspectives and personalities. According to some scholars, the heterogeneity of board members have several benefits, including adding diversity to the board's way of thinking and encouraging creativity and innovation which enhance organisational performance. Others contend that because of the

diversity, the board might have more conflict due to the divergent goals, and that it becomes more of a hindrance than help, and less effective in decision making.

The Central Bank of Nigeria noted that the adoption of a strong culture of corporate-governance (CBN, 2014) has not yet been embraced by many organisations in Nigeria. In a report by the Securities and Exchange Commission, over 40 per cent of the registered companies in Nigeria, including banks, were not adhering to the corporate-governance code which was set up in 2003. This non-compliance is responsible for myriad issues in the banking industry such as insider abuse, faulty reporting, failure to meet regulatory requirements, weak internal control and a lack of proactive planning for business trends.

Previously conducted studies yield conflicting results, which are partly due to the varying definitions of board diversity, which seem to be influenced by the institutional, cultural and economic characteristics of industries or economies. There is limited research on this subject in Nigeria, and the existing studies seem inconclusive. For example, Garba and Abubakar (2014) focused on financial-service firms in Nigeria, while excluding manufacturing firms. This study therefore presents fresh evidence on the impact of board diversity on the financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria and investigates additional proxies for board diversity that prior studies have overlooked.

Review of Related Literature

Theoretical Review

Agency Theory

According to agency theory, many of the corporate managers are agents appointed to manage the business of the firm on behalf of the owners of the firm instead of being the proprietor of the business (Ujunwa et al., 2012). Fama and Jensen (1983), according to Kilic (2015), argue that the role of the board of directors is one of the key mechanisms to monitor and control managerial decisions, and is an important determinant of corporate managerial policy. The board aims at reducing the agency issue between the management and the shareholders (Dang et al., 2013). In this view, women and foreign directors would be able to contribute to the effectiveness of the board and, consequently, the success of the organisation, with the essence of diversity being that it would minimise the risks of groupthink amongst the directors (Ujunwa et al., 2012). Agency theories propose that bringing in outside stakeholders (females, ethnic minorities, foreigners) can bring new ideas to complex problems (Francoeur et al., 2007). Female directors, for instance, may be more proactive in monitoring and controlling of the managers, by asking more questions and by providing other perspectives in the boardroom (Dang et al., 2013), while diversity may also enhance the independence of the board as board members from different cultural backgrounds, gender, or races may ask different questions, which conventional directors may not have thought of (Carter et al., 2013).

Resource Dependence Theory

The resource dependence theory lists four main benefits of external linkages: providing resources, improving communication with stakeholders, gaining support from powerful external actors and lending legitimacy. Boards of directors play a key role in managing externalities, environmental uncertainty and in the reduction of transaction costs (Dang et al., 2013). The theory suggests that board diversity can serve as a keyway to secure resources (Johnson et al., 2016), as each director brings unique skills and qualities and a variety of resources, such as knowledge, skills, information, and potential connections to stakeholders, to the board (Hillman et al., 2010). Firms may consciously change their boards' composition to address external environmental change and thus reduce uncertainty (Hillman et al., 2010). Some researchers also highlight the importance of the unique information and expertise that international directors can offer to companies on their home markets (Gull et al., 2018), and

how they can influence the companies' priorities, perspective on stakeholders and adaptability to environmental changes due to their cultural values and experiences (Harjoto et al., 2019).

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory is a key theory in corporate governance which changes the understanding of corporate governance from the traditional shareholder-centric to a broader view of all stakeholder groups that are impacted by a company's actions. It was stated by R. Edward Freeman in the 1980s that firms should consider the concerns of various stakeholder groups (employees, customers, suppliers, the community, and shareholders) in their decision-making process. This method can lead to more ethical, sustainable and socially responsible business practices and, consequently, greater chances of improving a company's reputation, operational viability and financial success (Richter & Dow, 2017).

The theory is that companies are embedded in a network of relations and, therefore, have to behave in a way that takes account of the interrelated and interdependent character of the network. Freeman claims that a firm's success depends not only on shareholder wealth maximisation but also on balancing the needs and concerns of the various stakeholders to create trust and teamwork between those who affect or are affected by the firm's operations. Stakeholder theory emphasizes that board members should be diverse in terms of diversity to reflect the broad stakeholder base of the firm, with each member bringing unique ideas and perspectives to guide comprehensive decision-making processes (Duran & Rodrigo, 2018).

The stakeholder theory is very attractive because it is comprehensive but may be difficult to apply. Because of the need for negotiation and compromise among the often-divergent interests of various groups of stakeholders, decision-making may be delayed, and there is a risk that the focus on profitability and returns to shareholders would become diffuse, rendering a business less competitive. Board diversity, based on the stakeholder theory, is however highly advantageous in Nigeria in the manufacturing sector (King'wara, 2020). Including directors from diverse geographical, ethnic and professional backgrounds can help manufacturing companies better understand the unique local market dynamics, issues and regulations. Having a diverse board can help to ensure that a range of views are considered in setting the strategy and operating the business, which helps to align the firm with stakeholder expectations and enhance their social licence to operate, governance and sustainability.

Empirical Review

Gordini and Rancati (2017) investigated the link between board age diversity and firm performance in Italy and found that there was a significant positive association. However, the study of Marinova et al. (2016) examining the influence of board diversity on firm performance, based on a two-stage least-squares estimation approach for a sample of 186 firms from Netherlands and Denmark, revealed that board diversity did not have a significant impact on firm performance.

This study was one of the studies that was carried out by Darmadi (2011) on the effect of board diversity on the performance of companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The study analysed the performance of 169 publicly traded companies, and it found that gender diversity was negatively and significantly related to performance, younger directors were positively related to performance, and nationality diversity was not significantly related to performance. EmadEldeen et al. (2021) filled another research gap by analyzing the impact of board composition, specifically board diversity on corporate performance using cross sectional data from non-financial firms listed on the London Stock Exchange (FTSE 350) between the years 2000-2016, they found that age diversity had a negative impact on firm performance while education diversity had a negative impact on firm performance which

means younger boards have a positive impact on firm performance and that investors may interpret educational diversity as a sign of intra-board conflict.

Ngo et al. (2019) assessed the effect of diversity in the board on the financial performance of the companies in the Vietnamese stock exchange by employing proxies of gender, nationality, education and age as diversity factors. Using a variety of different analyses—including pooled OLS regression—of the data of 482 companies that went public between 2015 and 2017, they identified a positive relationship between the percentages of female members, international members, and members with postgraduate education and financial performance, with no significant relationship found for the percentage of members younger than 45 years.

Ujunwa (2012) investigated 122 quoted companies in Nigeria to determine the impact of board attributes (gender, nationality and ethnicity and educational attainment – proxied by the presence of a PhD) on the performance of the companies from 1991 to 2008 and concluded that gender had a negative impact on corporate performance while nationality and ethnicity and educational attainment (proxied by the presence of a PhD) had positive impact on corporate performance. Shukeri et al. (2012) conducted a study on board attributes of quoted Malaysian firms and concluded that ethnic diversity had a positive impact on the performance of the firm whereas board independence had a negative impact. Chen (2015) studied 2,400 public and private companies in 18 cities in China and found that the more external directors a firm had the less government support it would receive and the less support a firm had in institutional quality, the more external directors it hired to enhance performance.

Carter, D'Souza, et al. (2010) investigated how diversity in the boardroom (females and ethnic-minority directors) affects the performance of U.S. companies and did not see a significant relationship. Cook and Glass (2015) examined the impact of ethnic minority board directors on performance, using panel data analysis and found a strong link between effective governance and performance and a diverse board. Assenga (2021) found that foreign directors add value to performance as they offer effective oversight and guidance to the CEO and senior management, and EmadEldeen et al. (2021) found national diversity to enhance performance. Tarigan et al. (2018) investigated board diversity in the manufacturing sector in Indonesia, which is the manufacturing sector that contributes the largest portion to the GDP in Indonesia, with 525 firm-year observations from 105 manufacturing companies that are listed on the stock exchange and found that nationality heterogeneity positively affected the level of financial performance but educational diversity did not. Harjoto et al. (2019) also showed that when boards are made diverse in terms of education, this enhances a strategic discussion, which in turn allows boards to develop a greater diversity of options, more effectively consider possible outcomes and create more imaginative solutions.

With regard to gender diversity in particular, Lee-Kuen et al. (2017) investigated the relationship between board gender diversity and the performance of Bursa Malaysia listed firms (2009 – 2013), using four proxies of board gender diversity, binary indicator of the presence of women, percentage of female directors, Blau index, Shannon index, and performance was proxied by Tobin's Q, and they found that three of the four proxies – percentage of female directors, Blau index, and Shannon index, were found to have a positive relationship with financial performance. Amadi et al. (2023) examined the effect of the presence of female board members on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and performance in A-share listed companies in China, and found that the number of female directors, their absolute age and educational background had significant impact on both CSR and financial performance, while CSR performance had a significant impact on financial performance.

In the same vein, Aziekwe and Okegbe (2024) explored the impact of nationality, gender and age diversity of board of directors on cash-flow return on investment of quoted consumer-goods companies in Nigeria, controlling for the effect of firm size. They conducted an ex-post-

facto design using a purposive sample of fifteen firms from twenty-one quoted companies in consumer goods and panel-corrected standard-errors regression using secondary data from 2013 to 2022, which showed that nationality diversity had negative but insignificant effect ($p = .359$), gender diversity had positive but insignificant effect ($p = .080$) and age diversity had positive and significant effect ($p = .007$). Matthew et al. (2023) tested the impact of gender diversity on the performance of quoted fast-moving consumer goods and industrial companies in Nigeria between January 2016 and December 2022, with gender diversity captured by the percentage of female directors on the audit committee, percentage of female directors on the board and independence of the board, and performance measured as the asset-efficiency ratio; they found that there was a negative and statistically significant association between the gender-diversity variables and performance. Lastly, Pandey et al. (2023) examined how board gender diversity is related to financial outcomes using complexity theory and qualitative comparative analysis on 204 non-financial companies on the Bombay Stock Exchange, finding that board gender diversity does not directly impact financial outcomes but does interact with other board and firm characteristics either positively or negatively while also being associated with reduction in the negative relationship between CEO duality and financial outcomes.

Hypotheses Development

Drawing on the theoretical and empirical literature reviewed above, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between age diversity and the financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between gender diversity and the financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between nationality diversity and the financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between educational diversity and the financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Methodology

A retrospective (ex-post-facto) research design was adopted. Secondary data were obtained from the audited annual reports of the sampled firms, focusing on age diversity, gender diversity, educational diversity, nationality diversity, and financial performance over the ten-year period from 2013 to 2022, yielding a balanced panel of 100 firm-year observations. The Hausman test was employed to determine the appropriate model between fixed effects and random effects: a significant p-value (generally below 0.05) indicates that the fixed-effects model is preferable, since it implies that the individual-specific effects are correlated with the included regressors, thereby violating the assumptions of the random-effects model. The choice between the fixed- and random-effects specifications was therefore governed by the Hausman test result, ensuring that the modelling approach was statistically sound and appropriate for the data structure and research aims.

Financial performance was proxied by return on assets (ROA), while board diversity was captured through four proxies: age diversity (AGDV), gender diversity (GNDDV), educational diversity (EDDV), and nationality diversity (NATDV). The general form of the multiple-regression model is expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \mu \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where Y is the dependent variable, β_0 is the constant, β_1 – β_n are the coefficients of the explanatory variables, X_1 – X_n are the explanatory variables, and μ is the error term.

Following the general specification and referencing Bakang (2015), the functional relationship between board diversity and financial performance is expressed as:

$$ROA = f(AGDV, GNDDV, EDDV, NATDV) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Reorganising equation (2) in econometric form gives the estimated model:

$$ROA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1AGDV_t + \beta_2GNDDV_t + \beta_3EDDV_t + \beta_4NATDV_t + \mu \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	ROA	AGDV	GNDDV	EDDV	NATDV
Mean	0.082164	57.74000	20.19236	3.000000	19.23029
Median	0.073732	58.00000	22.22222	3.000000	19.09091
Maximum	0.264935	61.00000	50.00000	4.000000	28.57143
Minimum	-0.088296	55.00000	0.000000	2.000000	8.333333
Std. Dev.	0.076188	1.088229	10.13119	0.426401	6.010065
Skewness	0.255493	-0.132304	0.487179	2.36E-17	-0.010608
Kurtosis	2.809320	6.187777	3.159068	5.555556	2.089838
Jarque-Bera	1.239436	42.63309	4.061153	27.21193	3.453524
Probability	0.538096	0.000000	0.131260	0.000001	0.177859
Observations	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Authors' computation, 2024. ROA = return on assets; AGDV = age diversity; GNDDV = gender diversity; EDDV = educational diversity; NATDV = nationality diversity (n = 100).

Return on assets (ROA). The average ROA for the firms was 8.22% (SD = 7.62%), indicating heterogeneity in the efficiency with which firms generate profit from their assets. ROA ranged from -8.83% to 26.49% with a median of 7.37%, a broad spread that reflects considerable disparities in asset-utilisation efficiency across firms. The distribution exhibited a skewness of 0.26 (a slight rightward tail) and a kurtosis of 2.81 (marginally flatter than normal); the Jarque-Bera test ($\chi^2(1) = 1.24, p = .538$) indicated that the departure from normality was not statistically significant.

Age diversity (AGDV). The mean age-diversity score was 57.74 (SD = 1.09), signifying limited variation across firms. Scores ranged from 55 to 61 with a median of 58. The distribution showed a slight negative skewness (-0.13) and a kurtosis of 6.19 (more peaked than normal), and the Jarque-Bera test revealed a significant departure from normality ($\chi^2(1) = 42.63, p < .001$).

Gender diversity (GNDDV). Average gender diversity was 20.19% (SD = 10.13%), indicating substantial variability across firms, with values ranging from 0% to 50% and a median of 22.22%. The distribution displayed a positive skewness (0.49) and a kurtosis of 3.16 (marginally more peaked than normal); the Jarque-Bera test ($\chi^2(1) = 4.06, p = .131$) indicated no significant departure from normality.

Educational diversity (EDDV). Educational diversity had a mean and median of 3.00 (SD = 0.43), suggesting that most firms possessed a comparable level of educational diversity, with values ranging from 2 to 4. The skewness was approximately zero (2.36E-17), indicating symmetry, while the kurtosis of 5.56 implied a more peaked distribution; the Jarque-Bera test ($\chi^2(1) = 27.21, p < .001$) revealed a significant departure from normality, pointing to the presence of outliers or an atypical distributional shape.

Nationality diversity (NATDV). Nationality diversity averaged 19.23% (SD = 6.01%), indicating moderate variation in the representation of different nationalities, with values ranging from 8.33% to 28.57% and a median of 19.09%. The distribution exhibited near-zero skewness (-0.01) and a kurtosis of 2.09 (marginally less peaked than normal); the Jarque-Bera test ($\chi^2(1) = 3.45, p = .178$) indicated no significant departure from normality.

Correlation Analysis

Table 2. Correlation matrix

	ROA	AGDV	GNDDV	EDDV	NATDV
ROA	1.000000				
AGDV	0.228838	1.000000			
GNDDV	-0.186045	-0.050252	1.000000		
EDDV	0.192056	0.087073	0.053923	1.000000	
NATDV	-0.150987	0.130726	0.385655	-0.046249	1.000000

Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

The correlation analysis between return on assets (ROA) and the diversity measures reveals nuanced links between financial performance and board diversity. A modest positive association is observed between ROA and both age diversity ($r = 0.229$) and educational diversity ($r = 0.192$), suggesting that firms with broader age and educational diversity tend to record marginally superior financial performance; such variety may supply insights and competencies that improve decision-making and operational efficiency, thereby supporting profitability. Conversely, a slight negative association is observed between ROA and both gender diversity ($r = -0.186$) and nationality diversity ($r = -0.151$), indicating that increases in these dimensions are marginally correlated with lower ROA. Although these negative associations are modest, they underscore the complexity of the relationship between diversity and financial performance and the importance of examining it within a multivariate framework.

Regression Analysis

$$ROA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1AGDV_t + \beta_2GNDDV_t + \beta_3EDDV_t + \beta_4NATDV_t + \mu \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Hausman Test

The Hausman test is a statistical procedure used to choose between a fixed-effects and a random-effects model in panel-data analysis. It evaluates the null hypothesis that the random-effects model is preferred against the alternative that the fixed-effects model is more appropriate, owing to correlation between the individual effects and the regressors.

Table 3. Hausman test

Correlated Random Effects – Hausman Test			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	11.614686	4	0.0205

Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

As shown in Table 3, the Hausman test produced a chi-square statistic of 11.614686 with 4 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.0205. Because the p-value is below the 5% significance level ($0.0205 < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative, indicating that the fixed-effects model is the more appropriate specification for the data.

Fixed-Effects Regression Results

Table 4. Fixed-effects regression results (dependent variable: ROA)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.761421	0.317389	-2.399018	0.0186
AGDV	0.012608	0.005490	2.296432	0.0241
GNDDV	0.002236	0.000719	3.110462	0.0025
EDDV	0.001592	0.000792	2.008575	0.0474
NATDV	0.003701	0.001637	2.260629	0.0350
R-squared	0.639694	Mean dependent var		0.082164
Adjusted R-squared	0.585230	S.D. dependent var		0.076188
F-statistic	11.74510	Durbin-Watson stat		1.491951

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Authors' computation, 2024. Method: panel least squares (fixed effects).

Constant (C). The constant term is -0.761421 (SE = 0.317389 ; $t = -2.399018$; $p = 0.0186$), and is statistically significant at the 5% level, implying that when all explanatory variables are zero the expected value of ROA is -76.14% , a purely hypothetical baseline in this context.

Age diversity (AGDV). The coefficient of 0.012608 indicates that a one-unit increase in age diversity is associated with a 1.26% rise in ROA, holding other variables constant. The effect is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0241$), demonstrating a beneficial effect of age diversity on financial performance.

Gender diversity (GNDDV). Gender diversity exerts a statistically significant positive effect on ROA (coefficient = 0.002236 ; $p = 0.0025$); a one-unit increase corresponds to a 0.22% rise in ROA, indicating that gender diversity favourably influences financial performance.

Educational diversity (EDDV). The coefficient of 0.001592 indicates that a one-unit increase in educational diversity is associated with a 0.16% rise in ROA, an effect that is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0474$) and underscores the beneficial impact of educational diversity on performance.

Nationality diversity (NATDV). The coefficient of 0.003701 indicates that a one-unit increase in nationality diversity corresponds to a 0.37% rise in ROA; the effect is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0350$), suggesting that nationality diversity enhances financial performance.

The adequacy of the model is supported by an R-squared of 0.639694 , indicating that approximately 64% of the variation in ROA is explained by the diversity variables, and by an adjusted R-squared of 0.585230 , which accounts for the number of predictors. The F-statistic of 11.74510 , with a p-value approaching zero, confirms the overall statistical significance of the model, while the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.491951 indicates negligible autocorrelation among the residuals. Collectively, these results provide persuasive evidence that diversity in age, gender, education, and nationality positively influences firm financial performance, underscoring the importance of diversity management in enhancing corporate outcomes.

Test of Hypotheses

The coefficient for age diversity (AGDV) is 0.012608 ($p = 0.0241$). Since the p-value is below 0.05 , the null hypothesis H_{01} is rejected, indicating a significant relationship between age diversity and financial performance, with age diversity positively associated with ROA. The coefficient for gender diversity (GNDDV) is 0.002236 ($p = 0.0025$); the null hypothesis H_{02} is therefore rejected, indicating a significant and positive relationship between gender diversity and ROA. The coefficient for nationality diversity (NATDV) is 0.003701 ($p = 0.0350$), leading to the rejection of H_{03} and confirming a significant positive relationship between nationality diversity and ROA. Finally, the coefficient for educational diversity (EDDV) is 0.001592 ($p = 0.0474$); as this value is below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis H_{04} is rejected, indicating a significant positive relationship between educational diversity and ROA.

Discussion of Findings

The positive relationship between age diversity (AGDV) and return on assets (ROA) supports the view that a mix of age demographics within a firm can enhance financial performance. Age diversity introduces a range of viewpoints, experiences, and problem-solving abilities, thereby strengthening creativity and innovation. This is consistent with prior evidence linking age variety to improved organisational performance and more effective decision-making (Richard et al., 2004).

The significant positive relationship between gender diversity (GNDDV) and ROA highlights the value of gender inclusion in corporate settings. This aligns with social-identity theory,

which suggests that firms benefit from a broader array of ideas, perspectives, and leadership styles. Evidence reported by Catalyst (2011), among others, indicates that firms with greater gender diversity on their boards and in senior roles often outperform less diverse peers, reinforcing the economic case for gender inclusiveness.

The beneficial effect of nationality diversity (NATDV) on ROA further illustrates the merits of a diverse board. National diversity can improve a firm's adaptability, cross-cultural competence, and global strategic outlook, which are increasingly vital in an interconnected economy. Oxelheim and Randøy (2003) similarly find that board-level transnational diversity can enhance firm value, particularly for firms with international operations, by deepening their understanding of, and access to, foreign markets.

Finally, the positive association between educational diversity (EDDV) and ROA underscores the advantage of appointing directors with varied educational backgrounds. Diverse educational experiences can foster innovative thinking, broaden a firm's knowledge base, and promote more effective problem-solving. This finding is consistent with the resource-based view of the firm, which holds that diversity in human capital constitutes a valuable and distinctive resource capable of conferring competitive advantage (Barney, 1991).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study provided a thorough analysis of the influence of board diversity on the financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria, focusing on age, gender, nationality, and educational diversity. The analysis of age diversity revealed a significant positive relationship with financial performance, suggesting that a variety of generational viewpoints within the boardroom improve decision-making and strategic direction. The examination of gender diversity likewise demonstrated a significant positive relationship, underscoring the importance of gender inclusivity in fostering a more dynamic and innovative corporate culture that enhances financial well-being. The investigation of nationality diversity revealed a beneficial relationship with performance, indicating that integrating diverse national perspectives cultivates a more comprehensive grasp of global markets and improves competitiveness. Educational diversity was also found to exert a positive effect on financial performance, implying that a diverse range of educational backgrounds strengthens a firm's capacity to navigate the complexities of the global market. Taken together, the findings confirm that board diversity enhances corporate governance and financial performance and that an inclusive board environment leverages varied perspectives for competitive advantage.

Recommendations

1. Corporations should establish and enforce policies that advance gender equality on their boards, including targeted recruitment, mentorship initiatives, and career-advancement programmes designed to increase the representation of women, younger members, and highly educated individuals in leadership roles.
2. Firms should deliberately broaden the age profile of their boards, since generational diversity was found to enhance decision-making and financial performance; succession planning should therefore balance experience with the inclusion of younger directors.
3. Manufacturing companies operating in, or aspiring to, international markets should consider appointing directors of diverse nationalities to strengthen cross-cultural competence, global market insight, and competitiveness.
4. Boards should value educational diversity in director selection, drawing on a range of academic and professional backgrounds to widen the firm's knowledge base and improve strategic problem-solving.
5. Regulators and policymakers, including the Securities and Exchange Commission and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, should strengthen disclosure requirements and codes of best practice relating to board-diversity reporting to promote transparency and accountability among quoted firms.

References

- Abdullah, S. N. (2004). Board composition, CEO duality and performance among Malaysian listed companies. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 4(4), 47–61.
- Abdullah, S. N., & Ismail, K. N. I. K. (2013). Gender, ethnic and age diversity of the boards of large Malaysian firms and performance. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, 38, 27–40.
- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291–309.
- Adams, S. M., & Flynn, P. M. (2005). Local knowledge advances women's access to corporate boards. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 13(6), 836–846.
- Ahmed, A., Monem, R. M., Delaney, D., & Ng, C. (2017). Gender diversity in corporate boards and continuous disclosure: Evidence from Australia. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 13(2), 89–107.
- Akintoye, I. R. (2016). *Investment decisions in the 21st century*. Unique Educational Publishers.
- Akpan, E. O., & Amran, N. A. (2014). Board characteristics and company performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(3), 81–89.
- Ali, R., Rehman, R. U., Suleman, S., & Ntim, C. G. (2022). CEO attributes, investment decisions, and firm performance: New insights from upper echelons theory. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 43(2), 398–417.
- Ali, S., Rehman, R. U., Ahmad, M. I., & Ueng, J. (2021). Does board diversity attract foreign institutional ownership? Insights from the Chinese equity market. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(11), 1–13.
- Amadi, C., Ode-Ichakpa, I., Guo, W., Thomas, R., & Dimopoulos, C. (2023). Gender diversity as a CSR tool and financial performance in China. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(2), Article 2207695.
- Assenga, M. P. (2021). Foreign directors and firm financial performance: Evidence from the Tanzanian listed companies. *Business Education Journal*, 10(1), 1–16.
- Aymen, B. M. M. (2018). Impact of capital on the financial performance of banks: The case of Tunisia. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 8(4), 47–54.
- Aziekwe, O., & Okegbe, T. O. (2024). Board diversity and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Global Accounting*, 10(1), 156–190.
- Bagh, T., Khan, M. A., Meyer, N., & Riaz, H. (2023). Impact of boardroom diversity on corporate financial performance. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10, Article 222.
- Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639101700108>
- Bassyouny, H., Abdelfattah, T., & Tao, L. (2020). Beyond narrative disclosure tone: The upper echelons theory perspective. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 70, Article 101499.
- Bear, S., Rahman, N., & Post, C. (2010). The impact of board diversity and gender composition on corporate social responsibility and firm reputation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 97(2), 207–221.
- Bertrand, M., & Schoar, A. (2003). Managing with style: The effect of managers on firm policies. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(4), 1169–1208.
- Bilimoria, D., & Wheeler, J. V. (2000). Women corporate directors: Current research and future directions. In R. J. Burke & M. C. Mattis (Eds.), *Women on corporate boards of directors* (pp. 138–163). Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Bjorklund, N. D. (2010). Boards of directors: A review and research agenda. *Journal of Management*, 22(3), 409–438.
- Campbell, K., & Mínguez-Vera, A. (2008). Gender diversity in the boardroom and firm financial performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 83(3), 435–451.
- Carpenter, M. A., Sanders, G., & Gregersen, H. B. (2001). Bundling human capital with organizational context: The impact of international assignment experience on multinational firm performance and CEO pay. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 44(3), 493–511.
- Carter, D. A., D'Souza, F., Simkins, B. J., & Simpson, W. G. (2010). The gender and ethnic diversity of US boards and board committees and firm financial performance. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 18(5), 396–414. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2010.00809.x>
- Carter, D. A., Simkins, B. J., & Simpson, W. G. (2003). Corporate governance, board diversity, and firm value. *The Financial Review*, 38(1), 33–53.

- Catalyst. (2011). *The bottom line: Corporate performance and women's representation on boards (2004–2008)*. Catalyst.
- Chaganti, R. (1986). Management in women-owned enterprises. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 24(4), 18–29.
- Chen, T. (2015). Institutions, board structure, and corporate performance: Evidence from Chinese firms. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 32, 217–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2014.10.009>
- Cook, A., & Glass, C. (2015). Do minority leaders affect corporate practice? Analyzing the effect of leadership composition on governance and product development. *Strategic Organization*, 13(2), 117–140.
- Dang, R., Nguyen, D. K., & Vo, L. C. (2013). *Women on corporate boards and firm performance: A comparative study*. IPAG Business School.
- Darmadi, S. (2011). Board diversity and firm performance: The Indonesian evidence. *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 8(2–4), 450–466. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv8i2c4p4>
- Díaz-Fernández, M. C., González-Rodríguez, M. R., & Simonetti, B. (2020). Top management team diversity and high performance: An integrative approach based on upper echelons and complexity theory. *European Management Journal*, 38(1), 157–168.
- Dobbin, F., & Jung, J. (2011). Corporate board gender diversity and stock performance: The competence gap or institutional investor bias? *North Carolina Law Review*, 89(3), 809–838.
- Duran, I. J., & Rodrigo, P. (2018). Why do firms in emerging markets report? A stakeholder theory approach to study the determinants of non-financial disclosure in Latin America. *Sustainability*, 10(9), Article 3111.
- EmadEldeen, R., Elbayoumi, A. F., Basuony, M. A. K., & Mohamed, E. K. A. (2021). The effect of board diversity on firm performance: An empirical study on the UK [Special issue]. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 18(3), 337–347.
- Farwis, M., Siyam, M. M., Nazar, M. C. A., & Aroosiya, M. A. C. F. (2021). The nexus between corporate governance and firm performance during the COVID-19 pandemic in Sri Lanka. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Accounting Studies*, 3(1), 81–88.
- Frijns, B., Dodd, O., & Cimerova, H. (2016). The impact of cultural diversity in corporate boards on firm performance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 41, 521–541.
- Garba, M. N., & Abubakar, B. D. (2014). Board diversity and organizational valuation: Unravelling the effects of ethnicity and gender. *Journal of Management and Governance*, 19(1), 167–195.
- García-Meca, E., García-Sánchez, I.-M., & Martínez-Ferrero, J. (2015). Board diversity and its effects on bank performance: An international analysis. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 53, 202–214.
- Gordini, N., & Rancati, E. (2017). Gender diversity in the Italian boardroom and firm financial performance. *Management Research Review*, 40(1), 75–94.
- Gottesman, A. A., & Morey, M. R. (2010). CEO educational background and firm financial performance. *Journal of Applied Finance*, 20(2), 70–82.
- Oxelheim, L., & Randøy, T. (2003). The impact of foreign board membership on firm value. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 27(12), 2369–2392. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4266\(02\)00395-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4266(02)00395-3)

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